

LITERARY FEATURES OF THE POEM “BEOWULF”
“BEOWULF” SHE’RINING ADABIY XUSUSIYATLARI
ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОЕМУ “БЕОВУЛФ”

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Abstarct. The **novelty** of the given article is predetermined by the fact that is the relevance of the characters in Beowulf, even though the poems are several hundred years old. This matter requires new and more efficient methods for research and analyses. Studying with deep analyses is the key task of modern literature researchers and teachers who deal with literature

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolaning yangiligi, she’rlar bir necha yuz yillik bo’lsa ham, Beowulf qahramonlarining dolzarbligi bilan belgilanadi. Bu masala tadqiqot va tahlillar uchun yangi va samaraliroq usullarni talab qiladi. Chuqur tahlillar bilan o’rganish zamonaviy adabiyotshunos olimlar va adabiyot bilan shug’ullanuvchi o’qituvchilarning asosiy vazifasidir.

Абстрактный. Новизна данной статьи определяется актуальностью персонажей «Беовульфа», несмотря на то, что стихотворениям несколько сотен лет. Этот вопрос требует новых и более эффективных методов исследования и анализа. Изучение с глубоким анализом – основная задача современных литературоведов и педагогов, занимающихся литературой.

Key words. Beowulf, poem, literary, monster, research, prince, Old English.

Kalit so’zlar. Beowulf, she’r, adabiy, yirtqich hayvon, tadqiqot, shahzoda, qadimgi ingliz tili.

Ключевые слова. Беовульф, поэма, литературный, чудовище, исследование, принц, древнеанглийский язык.

Introduction. The poem begins with a history of the Danish kings, starting with Shild (whose funeral is described in the Prologue) and leading up to the reign of the

current king Hrothgar, Shild's great-grandson. Hrothgar is well loved by his people and successful in war. He builds a lavish hall, called Herot (or Heorot), to house his vast army, and when the hall is finished the Danish soldiers gather under its roof to celebrate.

However, provoked by the singing and carousing of Hrothgar's followers, Grendel, a monster in human shape who lives at the bottom of a nearby swamp, appears at the hall late one night and kills thirty of the warriors in their sleep. For the next twelve years the fear of Grendel's potential fury casts a shadow over the lives of the Danes. Hrothgar and his advisers can think of nothing to appease the monster's anger.[3;34]

Results and discussion. Beowulf, prince of the Geats, hears about Hrothgar's troubles, and gathers fourteen of his bravest warriors, and sets sail from his home in southern Sweden. The Geats are greeted by the members of Hrothgar's court, and Beowulf boasts to the king of his previous successes as a warrior, particularly his success in fighting sea monsters. Hrothgar welcomes the arrival of the Geats, hoping that Beowulf will live up to his reputation. During the banquet that follows Beowulf's arrival, Unferth, a Danish soldier, voices his doubts about Beowulf's past accomplishments, and Beowulf, in turn, accuses Unferth of killing his brothers. Before retiring for the night, Hrothgar promises Beowulf great treasures if he meets with success against the monster. beowulf takes place in, beowulf, beowulf & Grendel.

That night, Grendel appears at Herot, and Beowulf, true to his word, wrestles the monster bare-handed. He tears off the monster's arm at the shoulder, but Grendel escapes, only to die soon afterward at the bottom of the snake-infested swamp where he and his mother live. The Danish warriors, who had fled the hall in fear, return singing songs in praise of Beowulf's triumph and performing heroic stories in Beowulf's honour. Hrothgar rewards Beowulf with a great store of treasures and, after another banquet, the warriors of both the Geats and the Danes retire for the night

Unknown to the warriors, however, Grendel's mother is plotting revenge for her son's death. She arrives at the hall when all the warriors are sleeping and carries off Esher, Hrothgar's chief adviser. Beowulf, rising to the occasion, offers to dive to the bottom of the lake, find the monster's dwelling place, and destroy her. He and his men follow the monster's tracks to the cliff overlooking the lake where Grendel's mother lives, where they see Esher's bloody head floating on the surface of the lake. Beowulf prepares for battle and asks Hrothgar to look after his warriors and to send his treasures to his uncle, King Higlac, if he does not return safely. During the ensuing battle, Grendel's mother carries Beowulf down to her underwater home, but Beowulf finally kills the monster with a magical sword that he finds on the wall of her home. He also finds Grendel's dead body, cuts off the head, and returns to dry land. The Geat and Danish warriors, waiting expectantly, celebrate as Beowulf has now purged.

Denmark of the race of evil monsters.

They return to Hrothgar's court, where the Danish king is duly thankful, but warns Beowulf against the dangers of pride and the fleeting nature of fame and power. The Danes and Geats prepare a great feast in celebration of the death of the monsters and the next morning the Geats hurry to their boat, anxious to begin the trip home. Beowulf bids farewell to Hrothgar and tells the old king that if the Danes ever again need help he will gladly come to their assistance. Hrothgar presents Beowulf with more treasures and they embrace, emotionally, like father and son. Beowulf and Grendel, Beowulf and Hrothgar, Beowulf and the Geats sail home and, after recounting the story of his battles with Grendel and Grendel's mother, Beowulf tells the Geat king Higlac about the feud between Denmark and their enemies, the Hathobards. He describes the proposed peace settlement, in which Hrothgar will give his daughter Freaw to Ingeld, king of the Hathobards, but predicts that the peace will not last long. Higlac rewards Beowulf for his bravery with parcels of land, swords and houses.[3;67]

In the second part of the poem, set many years later, Higlac is dead, and Beowulf has been king of the Geats for some fifty years. One day, a thief steals a jewelled cup from a sleeping dragon, and the dragon avenges his loss by flying through the night burning down houses, including Beowulf's own hall and throne. Beowulf goes to the cave where the dragon lives, vowing to destroy it single-handed. He is an old man now, however, and his strength is not as great as it was when he fought against Grendel. During the battle, Beowulf breaks his sword against the dragon's side and the dragon, engulfs Beowulf in flames, wounding him in the neck. All of Beowulf's followers flee except Wiglaf, who rushes through the flames to assist the aging warrior. Wiglaf stabs the dragon with his sword, and Beowulf, in a final act of courage, cuts the dragon in half with his knife.

Who is Beowulf, Beowulf unferth, unferth in Beowulf. However, the damage is done, and Beowulf realizes that he is dying, and that he has fought his last battle. He asks Wiglaf to take him to the dragon's storehouse of treasures, jewels and gold, which brings him some comfort and make him feel that the effort has perhaps been worthwhile. He instructs Wiglaf to build a tomb to be known as "Beowulf's tower" on the edge of the sea there.

After Beowulf dies, Wiglaf admonishes the troops who deserted their leader while he was fighting against the dragon, telling them that they have been untrue to the standards of bravery, courage and loyalty that Beowulf has taught. Wiglaf sends a messenger to a nearby encampment of Geat soldiers with instructions to report the outcome of the battle. The messenger predicts that the enemies of the Geats will feel free to attack them now that their great king is dead.

Wiglaf supervises the building of Beowulf's funeral pyre. In keeping with Beowulf's instructions, the dragon's treasure is buried alongside his ashes in the tomb, and the poem ends as it began, with the funeral of a great warrior [17;98]

Old English literature refers to poetry and prose written in Old English in early medieval England, from the 7th century to the decades after the Norman Conquest of 1066, a period often termed Anglo-Saxon England. The 7th century work Cadmon's Hymn is often considered as the oldest surviving poem in English, as it appears in an 8th-century copy of Bede's text, the Ecclesiastical History of the English People Poetry written in the mid 12th century represents some of the latest post-Norman examples of Old English. Adherence to the grammatical rules of Old English is largely inconsistent in 12th-century work, and by the 13th century the grammar and syntax of Old English had almost completely deteriorated, giving way to the much larger Middle English corpus of literature.

In descending order of quantity, Old English literature consists of sermons and saints' lives; biblical translations; translated Latin works of the early Church Fathers; chronicles and narrative history works; laws, wills and other legal works; practical works on grammar, medicine, and geography; and poetry. In all, there are over 400 surviving manuscripts from the period, of which about 189 are considered major. In addition, some Old English text survives on stone structures and ornate objects.

The poem Beowulf, which often begins the traditional canon of English literature, is the most famous work of Old English literature. The Anglo-Saxon Chronicle has also proven significant for historical study, preserving a chronology of early English history.

In addition to Old English literature, Anglo-Latin works comprise the largest volume of literature from the early medieval period in England.

"Beowulf" is the oldest known epic poem written in English, although its date is not known with any certainty (the best estimate being 8th Century CE, and definitely before the early 11th century CE). The author is likewise unknown, and represents a question that has mystified readers for centuries. It is generally thought that the poem was performed orally by memory by the poet or by a "scop" (a travelling entertainer), and was passed down in this way passed down to readers and listeners, or that it was finally written down at the request of a king who wanted to hear it again.

Because of the unified structure of the poem, with its interweaving of historical information into the flow of the main narrative, the poem was most likely composed by one person, although there are two distinct parts to the poem and some scholars believe that the sections which take place in Denmark and the sections which take place back in Beowulf's homeland were written by different authors. It is written in a dialect as Old English (also referred to as Anglo-Saxon), a dialect that had become the language of its time by about the early part of the 6th Century CE, in the wake of the

occupation of the Romans and the increasing influence of Christianity. Old English is a heavily accented language, so different from modern English as to appear almost unrecognizable, and its poetry is known for its emphasis on alliteration and rhythm. Each line of "Beowulf" is divided into two distinct half-lines (each containing at least four syllables), separated by a pause and related by the repetition of sounds. Almost no lines in Old English poetry end in rhymes in the conventional sense, but the alliterative quality of the verse gives the poetry its music and rhythm.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Beowulf symbolizes the ideal Anglo-Saxon hero. He is brave and has great inhuman strength. He is boastful but also lives up to his word. He has overcome many obstacles and is never one to give up. Beowulf's traits play a role that makes Beowulf so unstoppable. Beowulf seeks out glory by proving to himself and everyone else that he is the best. Even though, Beowulf dies in the end he also defeats his enemy gaining his glory. Beowulf is a great example of both an epic poem and hero because it conveys the main character with superhuman and heroic traits who faces continuous complications in a long period. When the guard says, "Nor have I seen a mightier man-at-arms on this earth than the one standing here: unless I am mistaken, he is truly noble."

This is no mere hanger-on in a hero's armour, it is clear that the poem depicts Beowulf as an honorable powerful being who is seen as everyone's savior. Beowulf had great qualities of a colossal hero. His heroism is because he never thinks of himself first. He has great physical strength. Beowulf also he stopped Grendel from killing any more of Hrothgar's men. Beowulf kills Grendel's mother with a sword. Beowulf performs several courageous deeds, risk his life for the greater good of everyone. He is glorified by all people. Beowulf would always put others first even if it meant putting himself in danger. Beowulf is a hero because he fought and won many battles. His last battle he had the upper hand but he was still killed. The dragon's poisonous venom killed him when he was dying.

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